

Original Research

ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) and Company Performance: ESG Guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance

Mega Silvia¹

Department of Accounting, Bina Darma University, Palembang, Indonesia

Fei Guo

Department of Accounting, Zhongnan University of Economics and Law,
Wuhan, China

Received 2 November 2024 Revised 26 November 2024 Accepted 28 November 2024

Abstract

The implementation of the sustainability concept through Environmental, social, governance (ESG) by companies is an important step to address global challenges related to sustainability issues. The ESG guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance are one of the efforts made by the Indonesian government to address sustainability issues. Unlike previous studies, this study uses the ESG guidelines in assessing ESG disclosures of Indonesian companies. It is necessary to analyze how the level of ESG disclosure of Indonesian companies based on these guidelines can affect the search for company performance focused on company value, cost of capital and carbon performance. This study aims to analyze the relevance of the implementation and disclosure of Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) based on these guidelines to company value, cost of capital, and carbon performance. This study uses a random effects model to analyze the relationship between variables with a sample size of 754 (Companies, years). The results show that ESG has a positive and significant effect on company value, ESG has a negative and significant effect on cost of capital, and ESG has a negative and significant effect on carbon performance. This study can explain that stakeholders are more interested in companies that seem to care about sustainability issues. The government needs to strive for more adequate regulations and sanctions to address sustainability issues and also protect stakeholders.

Keywords: Company Value, Cost of Capital, Carbon Performance, Environmental Accounting, Government Policy and Regulation.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: mega.silvia@binadarma.ac.id

Introduction

Companies with good performance can contribute greatly to the development of a country. This is because the dynamics of the economy of developing or developed countries have a significant impact from microeconomic factors, one of which is the business activities carried out by the company. Company performance is a benchmark for the company's success in achieving the company's sustainability goals.

Amidst the current sustainability issue, company performance can be seen from how the company's value, cost of capital and carbon performance. These three things are considered important, because previous research has involved these three aspects in the disclosure of Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) in companies, especially companies in Indonesia. This phenomenon indicates how important the positive image built by the company is in attracting stakeholders to invest in the company.

Companies that are able to gain legitimacy as companies that care about ESG issues have a great opportunity to become companies that are prioritized by stakeholders. The ESG concept is a basis that can be used to assess all business activities of an entity based on environmental, social, and governance aspects in order to support a sustainable business (Chvátalová & Šimberova, 2013) (Baalouch et al., 2019).

As explained by the Indonesian stock exchange in press release No.048/BEI.SPR/07-2021 that global challenges encourage various parties, one of which is domestic and foreign investors to invest in sectors that implement ESG. This is supported by the results of a global scale survey conducted by BNP Paribas Global, namely an increase of 20% of investors considering social aspects since the COVID-19 pandemic, then 79% of investors agreeing that considering social aspects will have a positive impact on long-term investment and their risk management (Oncioiu et al., 2020) (Sætra, 2021) (Park & Jang, 2021). Cooperation of all parties is needed to support the implementation of ESG in order to achieve sustainable development goals and overcome all global challenges (Machmuddah & Wardhani, 2020) (Almeyda & Darmansya, 2019) (Miklosik et al., 2021).

Recent studies have shown inconsistent results regarding the relationship between ESG, Cost of Capital, Company Value and Carbon Performance, such as research by Gutman et al., (2024); Kong et al., (2024); Q. Li et al., (2024); Treepongkaruna et al., (2024); C. Wang (2024); H. Xie et al., (2024); Zhang & Mao (2024). In Indonesia, research examining the relationship between ESG, Cost of capital, Company Value and Carbon Performance has been conducted by several researchers. Such as research by Pradana & Wijayanti (2024) which found that the Environmental and Governance aspects did not have a significant effect on the Cost of Capital, while the Social aspect had a positive and significant effect on the Cost of Capital.

Research by Sidi Rai & Ismawati (2024) found that the Environmental and Social aspects did not have a significant effect on the Cost of Capital, while the Governance aspect had a significant negative effect on the Cost of Capital. Research by Setiani et al., (2024) found ESG has a positive effect on financial performance and carbon performance.

Research by Zainuddin et al., (2024) found ESG has no effect on financial performance. Research by Saripulloh & Wedari (2024) found ESG has a negative effect on carbon performance as measured by carbon emission intensity.

The inconsistency of previous studies motivated this study to address the gap in research results by re-examining the relationship between ESG, Company Value, Cost of Capital, and Carbon Performance. Different from previous studies that used global ESG disclosure criteria as a measure of ESG disclosure. This study will use the ESG disclosure criteria owned by Indonesia, namely the ESG guidelines by the Ministry of Finance. This is because it would be more relevant to measure ESG disclosure in Indonesian companies using national measuring instruments that have never been used by previous studies. This is one of the innovations in this study.

The importance of analyzing ESG disclosure using national standards because ESG disclosure in Indonesian companies is not yet adequate when measured by several standards that are not managed by the Indonesian government. Research by Lubis & Rokhim (2021); Nisa et al., (2023) found that ESG disclosure of Indonesian companies based on GRI standards is still very low, less than 30%. By using national standards, this study can obtain more relevant results because it uses measuring instruments that have been adjusted to the conditions of Indonesian companies.

Through this study, the author will analyze how ESG disclosures that have been implemented by Indonesian companies today can have an impact on Company Value, Cost of Capital and Carbon Performance. It is important to re-examine the relationship between all these variables, because there are still inconsistencies in the research results. Through this study, it can also provide results that are more relevant to the situation in Indonesia, because this study uses national standards in measuring ESG disclosures of Indonesian companies. This is important because previous studies using global standards found that ESG of Indonesian companies was very low. The low achievement of ESG of Indonesian companies is because ESG disclosure in Indonesia is still voluntary. There are no regulations that require Indonesian companies to implement and disclose ESG. The emergence of ESG standards by the Indonesian Ministry of Finance is a turning point for Indonesian companies to prioritize ESG implementation in their business decision making. This is the right momentum to use national standards as an ESG measuring tool in this study.

Literature Review

ESG and Company Value

Research examining the relationship between Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) and Company Value has been widely conducted by previous researchers. Such as research by (Y. Li et al., 2018) found that the company's ESG disclosure had a significant impact on firm value. Pellegrini et al., (2019) found that companies that are able to adequately implement ESG will have high corporate values. Ionescu et al., (2019) found that the ESG component, particularly the governance aspect, had the most important impact on firm value. Miralles-Quirós et al., (2019) Environmental, social, governance have an effect on market value. Kraipornsak & Poramapojn (2021) book value, return on

assets, and firm size affect market value. Bahraini et al., (2021) profitability and leverage have an effect on market value.

Research by Velte (2017) found ESG disclosure has a positive impact on ROA but no impact on Tobin's Q. Research by Wang & Sarkis (2017) found that ESG had a significant and positive effect on ROA and Tobin's Q. Research by Atan et al., (2018) found no significant relationship between ESG and corporate profitability as measured by ROE and corporate value as measured by Tobin's Q. Research by Zhao et al., (2018) found ESG had a significant and positive effect on ROCE. Research by Duque-Grisales & Aguilera-Caracuel (2019) found that ESG had a negative and significant effect on ROA. Research by Xie et al., (2019) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on revenue earned and ROA.

Research by Shabbir et al., (2020) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on ROA, ROC and excess stock returns. Research by Kaiser (2020) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on Risk Adjusted returns. Research by Koundouri et al., (2021) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on ROA, ROE and Profit. Research by Abdi et al., (2021) found that governance has a significant and positive effect on financial performance as measured by the market to book ratio. Environmental and social have a significant and positive effect on company value as measured by Tobin's Q. Company size can mediate the relationship between ESG on financial performance and company value.

Research by Pulino et al., (2022) found ESG has a positive and significant effect on EBIT and ROA. Research by Wu et al., (2022) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on company value as measured by Tobin's Q. Research by Liu et al., (2022) found that Environmental has a significant negative effect on the company's financial performance, Governance has a significant positive effect on financial performance, and Social has no significant effect on financial performance. Overall ESG performance has a less significant impact on accounting-based financial performance and does not have a significant impact on market-based financial performance. Research by Gutman et al., (2024); Q. Li et al., (2024) found ESG disclosure can increase Company Value.

ESG and Carbon Performance

Research examining the relationship between ESG and carbon performance has been widely conducted by previous researchers. Environmental performance can be measured through achieving adequate carbon performance (Iswati & Setiawan, 2020) (Saraswati, 2020) (Garzón-Jiménez & Zorio-Grima, 2021) (Lu et al., 2021). Carbon performance is the company's success in reducing the intensity of carbon emissions by making the right decisions in carrying out all business activities (Hoffmann & Busch, 2008) (He et al., 2013) (Q.-C. Li & Long, 2019) (Choi et al., 2021). Research by Kolk et al., (2008) which used institutional theory which found that the level of disclosure of carbon emissions based on the CDP (Carbon Disclosure Project) showed a good development, so that in this case CDP has succeeded in using institutional investors to pressure companies to adequately disclose carbon emission information.

Stanny (2013) who uses stakeholder theory and legitimacy found that there are still many companies that do not disclose carbon emission information. Depoers et al., (2016) who use stakeholder theory and found that the disclosure of the amount of carbon emissions based on company reports was lower than based on the CDP (Carbon Disclosure Project). de Faria et al., (2018) who used legitimacy theory as the basic theory in analyzing the level of disclosure of carbon emissions and emissions. The level of disclosure that was achieved was 45.52% of the total level of disclosure in 48 companies registered as members of the CDP (Carbon Disclosure Project). Research by Kong et al., (2024) found a non-linear relationship between ESG and carbon emissions. Research by Treepongkaruna et al., (2024) found companies with high ESG disclosure do not have low carbon emissions. Research by H. Xie et al., (2024) found that companies with high ESG disclosure and implementation are motivated to reduce their carbon emissions, thus having adequate carbon performance.

ESG and Cost of Capital

Research examining the relationship between ESG and Cost of Capital has been conducted by quite a lot of previous researchers. Ahmed et al., (2019) found that companies with high environmental and social practices will have a low cost of capital. Pellegrini et al., (2019) found that companies with adequate ESG implementation have a significant impact on the company's cost of capital. Piechocka-Kaluzna et al., (2021) found that environmental, social, governance (ESG) has a significant effect on the cost of capital. Ramirez et al., (2022) found that the ESG component which includes environmental and social did not have a significant effect on the cost of capital, while the governance aspect had a negative effect on the cost of capital.

Research by Atan et al., (2018) found that individually, no ESG factor was significant to the cost of capital (WACC), but the combined ESG score had a positive and significant effect on the cost of capital (WACC). Research by Tian (2023) found ESG has a negative impact on the Company's Cost of Capital. Research by Pradana & Wijayanti (2024) which found that the Environmental and Governance aspects did not have a significant effect on the Cost of Capital, while the Social aspect had a positive and significant effect on the Cost of Capital. Research by Sidi Rai & Ismawati (2024) found that the Environmental and Social aspects did not have a significant effect on the Cost of Capital, while the Governance aspect had a significant negative effect on the Cost of Capital. Research by Saputra & Rahman (2023) found that the Environmental aspect has a positive effect on the cost of capital, the Social and Governance aspects have no effect on the cost of capital.

Hypothesis Development

ESG and Company Value

Referring to the legitimacy theory indicates that companies must operate in accordance with the values, norms, and expectations of society to gain social legitimacy. This legitimacy is an intangible asset that is important for the sustainability of the company, because it helps build stakeholder trust, reduces reputational risk, and creates broad support for the company's operations. Amidst the current sustainability issues, Indonesia is one of the countries that has begun to prioritize the implementation of ESG in the

business activities of Indonesian companies. This is evidenced by the emergence of the ESG Guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance in 2022 which can be used as a reference for Indonesian companies in making decisions and reporting their sustainability.

To gain legitimacy as a company that cares about sustainability issues and supports the implementation of these guidelines, Indonesian companies will certainly strive to implement ESG continuously. This is done to create the best reputation for the company in the eyes of stakeholders, so that the company's value will be high. Company value is an indicator that can be used by external and internal parties to determine the company's development and prospects in the future. To maintain its existence in the long term, the company needs support from stakeholders. This is because the focus of investors in assessing companies is becoming increasingly complex, namely covering social, environmental, and economic aspects simultaneously. Furthermore, the government as the party that makes the rules and policies also plays an important role in determining the success of the company in achieving the expected goals.

Entities that are able to implement ESG (environmental, social, governance) adequately based on government regulations are a form of compliance with the policies issued by the Indonesian government. Then, it can prove to stakeholders that all ongoing business activities are relevant to the concept of sustainable business, so that it will help the entity in increasing the company's value adequately. Thus, the first hypothesis in this study is:

H₁: Environmental, social, governance (ESG) has a positive effect on company value.

ESG and Cost of Capital

Referring to the legitimacy theory indicates that organizations need to act in accordance with the expectations and values of society in order to be considered legitimate. Social legitimacy can influence public perception, stakeholder trust, and access to economic resources, including capital. In the midst of the current sustainability content, companies are encouraged to commit to meeting societal expectations regarding environmental, social, and governance responsibilities. This can help reduce the perceived risks inherent in the company and increase its attractiveness to investors and creditors, which contributes to a lower cost of capital.

In 2022, Indonesia through the Indonesian Ministry of Finance launched the ESG Guidelines that can be used by Indonesian companies in implementing and disclosing ESG in sustainability reports. ESG disclosure in sustainability reports based on these guidelines can be a means for companies to gain legitimacy from stakeholders as companies that care about sustainability issues. The company's compliance with this national standard also proves that the company is committed to supporting the Indonesian government's efforts to start campaigning for the importance of ESG in carrying out business activities sustainably. Companies that are safe in overall aspects, and not limited to financial aspects, have a great opportunity to have a low cost of capital. The company is considered as a low-risk company in the eyes of stakeholders and can maintain its business in the long term. Thus, the second hypothesis of this study is:

H₂: Environmental, social, governance (ESG) has a negative effect on the cost of capital.

ESG and Carbon Performance

Referring to the legitimacy theory indicates that organizations must continuously adapt to societal expectations so that their activities are considered legitimate. Social legitimacy includes the perception that a company acts responsibly in its environmental and social management, which is important for maintaining good relations with stakeholders such as the government, the community, and investors. Indonesia is one of the countries that has begun to focus on implementing ESG in the company's business aspects. This is evidenced by the launch of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance's ESG guidelines in 2022. These ESG guidelines can be a foundation for Indonesian companies in implementing and disclosing ESG adequately.

Companies that are able to implement ESG adequately also have a great chance of successfully mitigating their carbon emissions. This is because the application of ESG in business decision-making is not limited to the company's ability to manage its finances. Companies with adequate ESG implementation, as evidenced by ESG disclosure in their sustainability reports, are companies that also pay attention to sustainability issues in making their business decisions. Thus, carbon emissions have become one of the main focuses to be immediately mitigated by companies as an important part of overcoming global problems and becoming one of the company's performance achievements in the era of sustainability. Thus, the third hypothesis in this study is:

H₃: Environmental, social, governance (ESG) has a positive effect on carbon performance.

Research Methods

ESG will be analyzed through ESG disclosure based on the ESG guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance. The author will observe the company's sustainability report to analyze the presence or absence of disclosure items referred to in this study. If there is, it is given a score of 1, and vice versa if there is none, it is given a score of 0. The environmental aspect consists of 16 disclosure items, the social aspect consists of 18 disclosure items, and the governance aspect consists of 6 disclosure items. In Indonesia, companies will disclose non-financial information, such as environmental, social and governance aspects in the sustainability report. Thus, the author will observe the sustainability report in assessing the company's ESG. The company value in this study will be proxied by Tobin's Q. Tobin's Q is used to measure the value of a company because it can provide effective information and reflect the company's overall financial performance. Tobin's Q can reflect market sentiment, such as company prospects or speculation.

The cost of capital in this study will be proxied by the weighted average cost of capital (WACC). WACC is chosen because it can determine the risk and potential return of an investment. The WACC figure can be a benchmark for investors to know the minimum return limit that must be obtained if investing funds in a particular company or project.

Carbon performance will be proxied by carbon emission intensity. Carbon emission intensity is the right parameter to assess the efficiency of carbon emissions of an activity or product, namely the comparison of the amount of carbon emissions produced to obtain a product or carry out a particular activity. Companies with a carbon emission intensity value above 1 will be given a weight of 1, while companies with a carbon emission intensity value below 1 will be given a weight of 2. The population in this study are all companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange that have sustainability reports for 2022 and 2023. 2022 is the year the ESG guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance were ratified.

The sample in this study is the entire population of 377 companies. Thus, the total sample data for this study is 754 (company-year). This study uses a random effect model in analyzing the relationship between variables. The random effect model is better used to overcome the problems of heteroscedasticity and correlation between times in data. The Random effect method can overcome the weaknesses of the Fixed effect method. Researchers will also conduct a robustness test to test the resilience of the variables in this study, as well as to validate the strength of a model. The robustness test is carried out by re-testing the relationship between ESG variables, company value, cost of capital and carbon performance by not combining ESG variables into one variable, but will be separated into Environmental, Social, Governance variables that stand alone. Thus, it can be seen how relevant each ESG aspect is to company value, cost of capital and carbon performance in Indonesian companies using the Ministry of Finance's ESG guidelines in the implementation and disclosure of ESG.

Results and Discussions

Results

The analysis results for ESG, Firm Value, Cost of Capital, Carbon Performance and control variable are presented in table 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1 Analysis Results of ESG, Company Value and Control Variables

Variable	Company Value (CV)			
	Coef.	std. error	t-value	p-value
ESG	0.436	0.177	3.981	0.002
ROI	0.331	0.209	3.001	0.016
Size	1.415	0.431	3.733	0.007
Leverage	-0.876	1.213	-1.012	0.411
Company Growth	1.081	0.108	4.263	0.000
Industry	0.169	1.513	0.012	0.993
N	754 (Company, Year)			
Adjusted R ²	0.522			
F Value	17.116			
Sig.	0.000			

The increase in ESG can increase company value by 0.436, the increase in ROI can increase company value by 0.331. The increase in Size can increase company value by

1.415, the increase in Company Growth can increase company value by 1.081. These results indicate that companies with adequate ESG disclosure, as well as increasing ROI, Size and Company Growth can maintain their existence in the long term, and are able to increase the company's reputation and value sustainably.

Table 2 Analysis Results of ESG, Cost of Capital and Control Variables

Variable	Cost of Capital (COC)			
	Coef.	std. error	t-value	p-value
ESG	-1.114	0.253	-4.325	0.001
ROI	0.872	0.378	1.274	0.121
Size	1.006	0.511	3.048	0.005
Leverage	-0.434	0.933	-0.362	0.872
Company Growth	-0.665	1.029	-0.114	0.995
Industry	0.724	0.906	0.635	0.563
N	754 (Company, Year)			
Adjusted R ²	0.436			
F Value	8.369			
Sig.	0.000			

Increasing the company's ESG can reduce the cost of capital by -1.114. Increasing the company's size can increase the cost of capital by 1.006. These results indicate that companies with adequate and increasing ESG implementation and disclosure capabilities can reduce their company's cost of capital, because these companies are considered to have a lower risk level than companies with little ESG disclosure. However, companies with large sizes also have high costs of capital. So, the bigger the company, the higher the cost of capital.

Table 3 Analysis Results of ESG, Carbon Performance and Control Variables

Variable	Carbon Performance (CP)			
	Coef.	std. error	t-value	p-value
ESG	-1.273	0.208	-3.067	0.008
ROI	1.342	0.125	4.127	0.002
Size	0.744	1.002	1.366	0.822
Leverage	0.661	0.982	1.808	0.547
Company Growth	0.903	0.195	3.066	0.007
Industry	0.446	1.021	0.1700	0.603
N	754 (Company, Year)			
Adjusted R ²	0.485			
F Value	10.931			
Sig.	0.000			

Increasing company ESG disclosure can decrease carbon performance by -1.273. Increasing ROI can increase carbon performance by 1.342. Increasing Company Growth can increase carbon performance by 0.446. These results indicate that companies with broader ESG disclosure have failed to mitigate their carbon emissions. Companies with increasing ROI and company growth have better carbon emission mitigation efforts.

Robustness Test

The results of the Robustness Test for the Environmental, Social, Governance, Company Value, Cost of Capital, Carbon Performance and Control Variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Analysis Results of Environmental, Social, Governance, Company Value, Cost of Capital, Carbon Performance, and Control Variables.

Variable	CV	COC	CP
Environmental	3.113**	-3.761**	-4.120**
Social	4.308**	-4.417**	-3.200**
Governance	3.514**	-3.550**	3.913**
ROI	4.011**	1.135	3.335**
Size	3.650**	4.125**	1.363
Leverage	-2.011	-1.008	1.438
Company Growth	3.717**	-1.119	4.050**
Industry	1.037	1.434	2.005
Adjusted R ²	0.493	0.456	0.471
F-Statistic	20.110**	16.648**	17.011**

The results of the analysis show that separately environmental disclosure has a positive and significant effect on company value. Environmental has a negative and significant effect on cost of capital and carbon performance. ROI has a positive and significant effect on company value and carbon performance. Size has a positive and significant effect on company value and cost of capital. Company Growth has a positive and significant effect on company value and carbon performance. While industry and leverage variables do not affect company value, cost of capital and carbon performance. Consistently, Environmental and Social variables have the same influence pattern on company value, cost of capital and carbon performance variables. While the governance variable has a different relationship pattern from before on carbon performance.

Discussion of Results

ESG and Company Value

Referring to table 1 shows that ESG variables have a positive and significant effect on company value. These results indicate that the broader the ESG disclosure made by the company, the more positive the response from stakeholders. These results are also relevant to the legitimacy theory which indicates that the company's ability to gain legitimacy as a company that cares about sustainability issues and supports the government through the implementation of applicable guidelines will improve the company's reputation.

Besides that, the increase in company value is also supported by other factors, such as company size, Return on Investment, and company growth. This provides evidence that large companies, with adequate company growth and high return on investment, tend to make extensive ESG disclosures to improve their business reputation and maintain their existence in the long term. This finding also proves that there is a tendency for stakeholders to prefer companies with extensive and adequate ESG disclosures.

In this case, the Government as a party capable of intervening in companies must further strengthen regulations related to sustainability issues. Regulations related to sustainability issues must also have a positive impact on stakeholders. Stakeholders also need to be protected to avoid greenwashing and other actions that may be taken by the company. As research by Silvia & Guo (2023); Silvia & Guo (2024) found that Indonesian companies have great potential to carry out greenwashing through sustainability reporting and media information. Their research also provides evidence that stakeholders are more interested in companies that are also active in providing information related to non-financial aspects, such as the environment, social, and governance. Thus, more adequate regulations are needed regarding sustainability issues amidst efforts to achieve current sustainable development goals.

The results of this study are also relevant to research by (Y. Li et al., 2018) found that the company's ESG disclosure had a significant impact on firm value. Pellegrini et al., (2019) found that companies that are able to adequately implement ESG will have high corporate values. Research by Abdi et al., (2021) found that Environmental and social have a significant and positive effect on company value as measured by Tobin's Q. Research by Wu et al., (2022) found that ESG has a positive and significant effect on company value as measured by Tobin's Q. Research by Gutman et al., (2024); Q. Li et al., (2024) found ESG disclosure can increase Company Value. Setiani et al., (2024) found ESG has a positive effect on financial performance.

ESG and Cost of Capital

Referring to table 2 shows that ESG has a negative and significant effect on the cost of capital. This result indicates that the wider the ESG disclosure made by the company, the lower the company's cost of capital. This result is also relevant to the legitimacy theory which indicates that the company's ability to gain legitimacy as a company that cares about sustainability issues and supports the government in implementing ESG guidelines will be directly proportional to the stakeholder response.

These findings indicate that stakeholders will respond well to the company's concern for sustainability issues. In the current era, it shows that stakeholders are not only

concerned with the company's ability to produce adequate financial performance, but also care about the company's ability to produce adequate performance in environmental, social and governance aspects. Sustainability issues are a new space that stakeholders want in assessing company performance. Companies with adequate sustainability performance are considered companies with a low level of risk. This is what ultimately drives the company's cost of capital to also decrease.

The research findings also show that large companies tend to disclose more ESG in their reports. This is also what can ultimately attract the attention of stakeholders to provide more value to the company. Stakeholders assume that large companies with adequate ESG disclosure can maintain their existence in the long term. Large companies with a high level of concern for sustainability issues are considered companies with a low level of risk in the eyes of stakeholders.

The results of this study are relevant to research by Ahmed et al., (2019) found that companies with high environmental and social practices will have a low cost of capital. Piechocka-Kaluzna et al., (2021) found that environmental, social, governance (ESG) has a significant negative effect on the cost of capital. Ramirez et al., (2022) found that governance aspect has a negative effect on the cost of capital. Research by Tian (2023) found ESG has a negative impact on the Company's Cost of Capital. Research by Sidi Rai & Ismawati (2024) found that the the Governance aspect has a significant negative effect on the Cost of Capital.

ESG and Carbon Performance

Referring to table 3 shows that ESG disclosure has a negative and significant effect on the company's carbon performance. This result indicates that the broader the company's ESG disclosure, the company's carbon performance tends to decline. The findings in this study indicate that the opposite of the legitimacy theory and the hypothesis of this study. The findings of the study indicate that companies with extensive ESG disclosure have failed to mitigate the company's carbon emissions. The findings in this study indicate that companies with adequate ESG disclosure are not necessarily companies with adequate environmental performance. Companies that fail to mitigate carbon emissions tend to make extensive environmental disclosures in their sustainability reports.

In this case, Indonesian companies have a great opportunity to carry out greenwashing. Companies that fail to achieve good environmental performance have the opportunity to carry out a series of activities to cover up the failure. These companies will adopt a series of relevant disclosures to show that their companies are free from failure to mitigate environmental pollution. Such decision-making is intended to attract the attention of stakeholders to be considered as companies that care about sustainability issues, when in fact this is not the case. These findings are also relevant to research conducted by Silvia & Guo (2023); Silvia & Guo (2024) which found that Indonesian companies have the potential to engage in greenwashing through sustainability reporting and other media, especially for companies that fail to mitigate environmental pollution. The results of this study are relevant to research by Treepongkaruna et al., (2024) found companies with high ESG disclosure do not have low carbon emissions. Silvia & Guo (2023) Companies that fail to mitigate carbon emissions will spread carbon more widely.

ESG, Company Value, Cost of Capital and Carbon Performance

Referring to table 4 shows that separately environmental, social, governance disclosure consistently has a significant effect on company value, cost of capital, and carbon performance. The results of this robustness test prove that even though the ESG components are retested separately against all dependent variables, the results remain consistent. The same thing also happens to all control variables.

These findings indicate that stakeholders are more interested in companies that not only have adequate financial performance, but also care about sustainability issues. Stakeholders consider that companies with extensive ESG disclosure are companies that care about sustainability issues. These companies are considered to be companies that have a low level of risk. Thus, these companies are considered to be companies that can maintain their existence in the long term.

However, another fact from this study is that most Indonesian companies that adopt adequate ESG disclosure are not directly proportional to the company's efforts to mitigate environmental pollution. Companies with increasingly extensive ESG disclosure levels have declining carbon performance. This indicates that there are company efforts to carry out greenwashing and other actions to cover up the company's failure to mitigate environmental pollution. These actions are also mostly carried out by large companies with adequate levels of company growth.

These findings can be input to the Indonesian government to start implementing more adequate regulations related to sustainability issues. The regulations that are built are also expected to provide protection to stakeholders so that they do not make mistakes in making decisions. Stakeholders also need to be careful in making investment decisions or providing credit. The Ministry of Finance's ESG guidelines are an important step that has been taken by the Indonesian government. In the future, there are strong mandatory regulations and adequate sanctions related to resolving sustainability issues and other environmental problems.

Conclusion

This study has successfully proven that stakeholders are more interested in companies that disclose more ESG in their sustainability reports. This indicates that companies with broader ESG disclosures are considered to be companies with lower risk levels and are concerned about sustainability issues. However, the problem is that broad ESG disclosures are not directly proportional to the company's efforts to mitigate environmental pollution, especially carbon emission mitigation. This indicates that some large companies in Indonesia have the potential to carry out greenwashing. The launch of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance's ESG guidelines is one of the initial steps of the Indonesian government to address sustainability issues. In the future, it is hoped that it can be a concern for the Indonesian government to strive for more adequate regulations and sanctions in addressing sustainability issues and protecting stakeholders from making mistakes in making decisions. The limitation of this study is that it has not examined in depth the differences in the level of compliance with the implementation and disclosure

of ESG before and after the implementation of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance's ESG guidelines in the companies that are the objects of the study.

References

- Abdi, Y., Li, X., & Càmara-Turull, X. (2021). Exploring the impact of sustainability (ESG) disclosure on firm value and financial performance (FP) in airline industry: the moderating role of size and age. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 0123456789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01649-w>
- Ahmed, D. A. H., Eliwa, Y., & Power, D. M. (2019). The impact of corporate social and environmental practices on the cost of equity capital: UK evidence. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 27(3), 425–441. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-11-2017-0141>
- Almeyda, R., & Darmansya, A. (2019). The Influence of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Disclosure on Firm Financial Performance. *IPTEK Journal of Proceedings Series*, 0(5), 278. <https://doi.org/10.12962/j23546026.y2019i5.6340>
- Atan, R., Alam, M. M., Said, J., & Zamri, M. (2018). The impacts of environmental, social, and governance factors on firm performance. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 29(2), 182–194. <https://doi.org/10.1108/meq-03-2017-0033>
- Baalouch, F., Ayadi, S. D., & Hussainey, K. (2019). A study of the determinants of environmental disclosure quality: evidence from French listed companies. In *Journal of Management and Governance* (Vol. 23, Issue 4). Springer US. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10997-019-09474-0>
- Bahraini, S., Endri, E., Santoso, S., Hartati, L., & Marti PRAMUDENA, S. (2021). Determinants of Firm Value: A Case Study of the Food and Beverage Sector of Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance*, 8(6), 839–0847. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no6.0839>
- Choi, B., Luo, L., & Shrestha, P. (2021). The value relevance of carbon emissions information from Australian-listed companies. *Australian Journal of Management*, 46(1), 3–23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0312896220918642>
- Chvátalová, Z., & Šimberova, I. (2013). Analysis of esg indicators for measuring enterprise performance. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 61(7), 2197–2204. <https://doi.org/10.11118/actaun201361072197>
- de Faria, J. A., Andrade, J. C. S., & da Silva Gomes, S. M. (2018). The determinants mostly disclosed by companies that are members of the Carbon Disclosure Project. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 23(7), 995–1018. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-018-9785-0>
- Depoers, F., Jeanjean, T., & Jérôme, T. (2016). Voluntary Disclosure of Greenhouse

- Gas Emissions: Contrasting the Carbon Disclosure Project and Corporate Reports. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 134(3), 445–461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2432-0>
- Duque-Grisales, E., & Aguilera-Caracuel, J. (2019). Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Scores and Financial Performance of Multilatinas: Moderating Effects of Geographic International Diversification and Financial Slack. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 168(2), 315–334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04177-w>
- Garzón-Jiménez, R., & Zorio-Grima, A. (2021). Effects of carbon emissions, environmental disclosures and csr assurance on cost of equity in emerging markets. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020696>
- Gutman, S. S., Egorova, M. M., Ibragimov, B. B., Nosirova, S. S., & Seytenova, V. (2024). The Relationship Between ESG Metrics and Financial Performance of an Enterprise in the Oil and Gas Sector. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 574(2024), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202457403004>
- He, Y., Tang, Q., & Wang, K. (2013). Carbon disclosure, carbon performance, and cost of capital. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 1(3–4), 190–220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21697221.2014.855976>
- Hoffmann, V. H., & Busch, T. (2008). Corporate carbon performance indicators: Carbon intensity, dependency, exposure, and risk. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 12(4), 505–520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2008.00066.x>
- Ionescu, G. H., Firoiu, D., Pirvu, R., & Vilag, R. D. (2019). The impact of ESG factors on market value of companies from travel and tourism industry. *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*, 25(5), 820–849. <https://doi.org/10.3846/tede.2019.10294>
- Iswati, S., & Setiawan, P. (2020). Green Earth: Carbon Emissions, ISO 14001, Governance Structures, Militarily Connected from the Manufacturing Industries in Indonesia. *Journal of Accounting and Investment*, 21(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.18196/jai.2101134>
- Kaiser, L. (2020). ESG integration: value, growth and momentum. *Journal of Asset Management*, 21(1), 32–51. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41260-019-00148-y>
- Kolk, A., Levy, D., & Pinkse, J. (2008). Corporate Responses to an Emerging Climate Regime: the Institutionalization and Commensuration of Carbon Disclosure. *European Accounting Review*, 17(4), 1–35. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1268404>
- Kong, X., Li, Z., & Lei, X. (2024). Research on the impact of ESG performance on carbon emissions from the perspective of green credit. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-61353-3>
- Koundouri, P., Pittis, N., & Plataniotis, A. (2021). The Impact of ESG Performance on

- the Financial Performance of European Area Companies: An Empirical Examination. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*, 15 (13)(September), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2022015013>
- Kraipornsak, P., & Poramapojn, P. (2021). Determinants of the Market Value of Listed Firms in the Services Sector: a Case of Thailand. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 13(1), 155–172. <https://doi.org/10.34109/ijefs.202112229>
- Li, Q.-C., & Long, Y. (2019). Research on the Carbon Performance Evaluation in the New Era—Based on the Full Life-Cycle Perspective. *International Conference on Economics and Management*, 278–282. <https://doi.org/10.12783/dtem/icem2019/31188>
- Li, Q., Tang, W., & Li, Z. (2024). ESG systems and financial performance in industries with significant environmental impact: a comprehensive analysis. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 5(6), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2024.1454822>
- Li, Y., Gong, M., Zhang, X., & Koh, L. (2018). The Impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance Disclosure on Firm Value: The Role of CEO Power. *The British Accounting Review*, 50(1), 60–75. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1243342>
- Liu, H., Wu, K., & Zhou, Q. (2022). Whether and How ESG Impacts on Corporate Financial Performance in the Yangtze River Delta of China. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(24), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416584>
- Lu, W., Zhu, N., & Zhang, J. (2021). The impact of carbon disclosure on financial performance under low carbon constraints. *Energies*, 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144126>
- Lubis, M. F. F., & Rokhim, R. (2021). The Effect of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Disclosure and Competitive Advantage on Companies Performance as An Implementation of Sustainable Economic Growth in Indonesia for Period of 2015-2019. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 940(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/940/1/012059>
- Machmuddah, Z., & Wardhani, R. (2020). *Environmental Social Governance (ESG) Disclosure Score Rating of Bloomberg. August*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/ahsr.k.200723.011>
- Miklosik, A., Starchon, P., & Hitka, M. (2021). Environmental sustainability disclosures in annual reports of ASX Industrials List companies. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(11), 16227–16245. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01338-8>
- Miralles-Quirós, M. M., Miralles-Quirós, J. L., & Redondo-Hernández, J. (2019). The impact of environmental, social, and governance performance on stock prices: Evidence from the banking industry. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(6), 1446–1456. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1759>

- Nisa, A. Z., Titisari, K. H., & Masitoh, E. (2023). Pengaruh Pengungkapan Environmental, Social, dan Governance (ESG) Terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan. *Al-Kharaj: Jurnal Ekonomi, Keuangan Dan Bisnis Syariah*, 1(19), 91–97. <https://doi.org/10.47467/alkharaj.v5i5.3410>
- Oncioiu, I., Popescu, D. M., Aviana, A. E., Șerban, A., Rotaru, F., Petrescu, M., & Marin-Pantelescu, A. (2020). The role of environmental, social, and governance disclosure in financial transparency. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(17), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12176757>
- Park, S. R., & Jang, J. Y. (2021). The impact of ESG management on investment decision: Institutional investors' perceptions of country-specific ESG criteria. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs9030048>
- Pellegrini, C. B., Caruso, R., & Mehmeti, N. (2019). The impact of ESG scores on cost of equity and firm's profitability. *The Research Centre of Applied Economics*, 10(3–4), 38–40. https://doi.org/10.22495/ncpr_9
- Piechocka-Kaluzna, A., Tluczak, A., & Lopatka, P. (2021). The Impact of CSR/ESG on the Cost of Capital: A Case Study of US Companies. *European Research Studies Journal*, XXIV(Special Issue 3), 536–546. <https://doi.org/10.35808/ersj/2510>
- Pradana, I. Z. A., & Wijayanti, I. (2024). The Influence of Environmental Social Governance (Esg) on Company Value With Financial Performance As a Moderating Variable. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*, 9(1), 34–45. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jaa.v9i1.423>
- Pulino, S. C., Ciaburri, M., Magnanelli, B. S., & Nasta, L. (2022). Does ESG Disclosure Influence Firm Performance? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(13), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14137595>
- Ramirez, A. G., David, J., Almonacid, P., & Peña, A. (2022). *Relationship between the Cost of Capital and Environmental, Social, and Governance Scores: Evidence from Latin America*.
- Sætra, H. S. (2021). A framework for evaluating and disclosing the esg related impacts of ai with the sdgs. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158503>
- Saputra, A., & Rahman, A. (2023). ESG Performance and Its Impact on Mitigating Cost of Capital: Evidence from Southeast Asia. *E-Journal of Accounting*, 34(8), 2054–2072. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJA.2024.v34.i08.p12>
- Saraswati, E. (2020). CARBON ACCOUNTING, DISCLOSURE AND MEASUREEMENT: A Systematic Literature Review. *The International Journal of Accounting and Business Society*, 28(2), 17–44. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.ijabs.2020.28.2.2>

- Saripulloh, A., & Wedari, L. K. (2024). Sustainability and Financial Performance: Examining ESG Disclosure And Carbon Intensity In Indonesia's High-Polluting Industries. *Journal of Logistics, Informatics and Service Science*, 11(8), 360–379. <https://doi.org/10.33168/jliss.2024.0821>
- Setiani, E. P., Dewanti, P. W., & Cortez, E. (2024). ESG Scores, Financial Performance, and Carbon Emissions : Evidence from Southeast Asian Companies. *Jurnal Nominal Barometer Riset Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 13(2), 227–238.
- Shabbir, M. S., Aslam, E., Irshad, A., Bilal, K., Aziz, S., Abbasi, B. A., & Zia, S. (2020). Nexus between corporate social responsibility and financial and non-financial sectors' performance: a non-linear and disaggregated approach. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(31), 39164–39179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09972-x>
- Sidi Rai, N. M. G. D., & Ismawati, A. F. (2024). The Influence of Esg Disclosure Score on the Cost of Capital in the Manufacturing Company. *Journal of Accounting, Entrepreneurship and Financial Technology (JAEF)*, 5(2), 81–102. <https://doi.org/10.37715/jaef.v5i2.3837>
- Silvia, M., & Guo, F. (2023). Determinants of Voluntary Carbon Disclosure in Indonesian Company : Greenwashing Risks. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 10(8), 551–573. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419436>
- Silvia, M., & Guo, F. (2024). Consequences of Carbon Disclosure in Indonesian Company : Requires Adequate Regulations. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 11(4), 402–427.
- Stanny, E. (2013). Voluntary Disclosures of Emissions by US Firms. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 22(3), 145–158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1732>
- Tian, X. (2023). ESG Rating and Cost of Capital. *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, 27(1), 224–230. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/27/20231267>
- Trepongkaruna, S., Au Yong, H. H., Thomsen, S., & Kyaw, K. (2024). Greenwashing, carbon emission, and ESG. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 15(7), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3929>
- Velte, P. (2017). Does ESG performance have an impact on financial performance? Evidence from Germany. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 8(2), 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-11-2016-0029>
- Wang, C. (2024). The Relationship between ESG Performance and Corporate Performance - Based on Stakeholder Theory. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 190(2024), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202419003022>
- Wang, Z., & Sarkis, J. (2017). Corporate social responsibility governance, outcomes,

and financial performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 162, 1607–1616.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.06.142>

Wu, S., Li, X., Du, X., & Li, Z. (2022). The Impact of ESG Performance on Firm Value: The Moderating Role of Ownership Structure. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114507>

Xie, H., Qin, Z., & Li, J. (2024). ESG performance and corporate carbon emission intensity: based on panel data analysis of A-share listed companies. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 12(October), 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1483237>

Xie, J., Nozawa, W., Yagi, M., Fujii, H., & Managi, S. (2019). Do environmental, social, and governance activities improve corporate financial performance? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(2), 286–300.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2224>

Zainuddin, Z., Wahab, N. A., Shari, W., Bahaman, M. A., & Yusof, R. M. (2024). The Impact of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Practices on the Financial Performance of Green Companies in Malaysia: An Empirical Analysis. *The Indonesian Capital Market Review*, 16(1), 55–66.
<https://doi.org/10.21002/icmr.v16i1.1177>

Zhang, Y., & Mao, G. (2024). Study of the Impact of ESG Performance on The Financial Performance of Mining Companies. *Frontiers in Business, Economics and Management*, 15(1), 126–133. <https://doi.org/10.54097/mrbw8f75>

Zhao, C., Guo, Y., Yuan, J., Wu, M., Li, D., Zhou, Y., & Kang, J. (2018). ESG and corporate financial performance: Empirical evidence from China's listed power generation companies. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(8), 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082607>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2024 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Silvia, M., & Guo, F. (2024). ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) and Company Performance: ESG Guidelines of the Indonesian Ministry of Finance. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(12), 1680-1698.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14454403</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_210438.html</p>	